

Assessment Of Emotional Intelligence Among Adolescents at Selected College in Tirupati

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study is to assess Emotional Intelligence among Adolescents at selected colleges in Tirupati, AP. Adolescence is a period of heightened emotionality. If the adolescents cannot perceive, understand, regulate and function with their emotions it will leave indelible marks on their behavior and personality. During adolescence, the transition from childhood to adulthood is most important. Children are becoming more independent, and begin to look at the future in terms of career, relationships, families, housing, etc. The individual wants to belong to a society and fit in. This is a major stage in development where the child has to learn the roles he will occupy as an adult. The purpose of the study was to assess the emotional intelligence of adolescent boys and girls. The sample consisted of 50 adolescent boys and 50 adolescent girls studying in the S.V. Arts College, TTD, Tirupati. Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Daniel Goleman was used. Results showed Data was analyzed and found that level of emotional intelligence among 100 students, 17(17%) had average, 12(12%) had above average, 49(49%) had superior and 22(22%) had excellent level. Girls in my study scored higher than boys value in total EI and its four sub scales and significance different boys and girls with their respect to subscale of emotional intelligence $p < 0.001$.

Keywords: Emotional Intelligence (EI), adolescents.

INTRODUCTION

Peter Salovey and John Mayer were the first researchers who created the term "emotional intelligence" in 1990. Their theory predominantly combines main ideas from the domains of intellect and emotion. The term "emotional intelligence" has generated a lot of interest since the publication of the book Emotional Intelligence by Daniel Goleman. The most basic definition of emotional intelligence (E. I.) which was designed by Goleman describes it as a skill to identify and control emotions within ourselves as well as of others. Emotional intelligence is one of the most popular research topics of the 21st century (Ashkanasy, 2003; Bar-On 2006), emphasizes on the role of emotions in an individual's success or failure in workplace and individuals. The adolescent is a crucial stage of a personality development as well as involves a lot of physiological and psychological changes, which directly effect on the personality of an individual. This stage approximately ranges from 16 to 20 years. It is also called "Stress and Storm Phase".

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Adolescence is the time when a person acquires the ability to think further than the present, envision its implication and the future, also grasp the complexity

of relationships. They encounter new experiences; unfamiliar situations often result in new and possibly intense positive and negative emotional reactions. There is a need to nurture the emotional intelligence skills for regulating their emotions and behaviour.⁸ Reuven Bar-On who helped coin the term "emotion quotient". He defines it as a individual trait which helps an individual understand oneself as well as others and it also helps the individual to adjust with the immediate surroundings thereby helping him/her in successfully coping with the environment demands. Emotional intelligence is, the ability and freedom to grow from mistrust to trust, self doubt to self-empowerment, following to leading, incompetence to competence, isolation to synergy, and despair to hope.¹¹

NEED FOR THE STUDY

Many people think that if an individual has a high level of intellect, the individual will have opportunity to achieve better success compares to those with low intellect. However, there were cases where people with high intellect who were left behind than those who have low intellect". Good and strong emotional intelligence of an individual could influence a student's level of academic performance. The stability

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of this element would not only have implications towards good achievement but also becomes the measure for good attitude of the students.¹⁷

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

ASSESSMENT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG ADOLESCENTS AT SELECTED COLLEGE IN TIRUPATI.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To assess and compare the level of emotional intelligence among adolescents boys and girls
- To associate the emotional intelligence of adolescents with their demographic variables
- To co-relate the subscales of emotional intelligence among adolescents

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

S.RAJAMANI; et al(2024)¹⁴: conducted “A comparative study on emotional intelligence, parenting style among adolescent students with special needs”. This study examined the influence of parenting styles on emotional intelligence of secondary school students in Chennai District. Forty (40) parent and 40 students were randomly selected from special schools with age ranging from 15 to 19 years (mean age-17 years) through stratified random sampling techniques. The study being a survey research, made use of a questionnaire consisting of two validated subscales; the Trait Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (TEIQue) and the Parenting Style Inventory (PSI). In testing the relationship between parenting styles and emotional intelligence, result shows that father's authoritative parenting style ($r = 0.152, p < .005$) and mother's authoritative parenting style ($r = 0.227, p < .01$) contributed to the prediction of emotional intelligence. Regression analysis shows that of the six predictor variables, only mother's authoritative parenting style ($\beta = 1.952, t = 2.345, p < .05$) could significantly predict the emotional intelligence of

senior school students. Being emotionally intelligent adds value to life.

METHODOLOGY

METHOD OF THE STUDY

For the present study the researcher has used Descriptive Survey method.

SAMPLE OF THE STUDY

The sample consisted of 100 adolescent students from the S.V.Arts Degree College TTD, Tirupati.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The sampling technique used was simple random sampling technique.

TOOLS FOR DATA COLLECTION

Development and description of tool:

Standardized questionnaire:

The following tools were used for collecting the data to measure the variables of the study.

Section: 1: Consists of questions related to demographic data of adolescent boys and girls.

Section: 2: Consists of standardized Daniel Goleman emotional Intelligence scale to assess emotional intelligence. It consists of 4 sub-components and 20 items related to our daily life.

Ethical consideration

1. The study was approved by the research committee and formal permission was taken from the Head of the institution.
2. Informed consent was obtained from the study samples, (adolescent).
3. The subjects were informed that their participation was purely on the voluntary basis and they can withdraw from the study at any time

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AMONG ADOLESCENCE

Frequency and percentage distribution of level emotional intelligence among adolescents
N=100

S.No	Emotional intelligence	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std. Deviation
1	Average	17	17.00	27.41	3.658
2	Above average	12	12.00	49.5	7.065
3	Superior	49	49.00	69.2	5.338
4	Excellent	22	22.00	85.55	5.561
	Total	100	100.00	63.33	19.989

INTERPRETATION: shows that level of emotional intelligence among 100 students 17(17%) had

average, 12(12%) had above average, 49(49%) had superior and 22(22%) had excellent level.

COMPARE EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE BETWEEN BOYS AND GIRLS Compare emotional intelligence between boys and girls
N=100

Emotional Intelligence between Boys and Girls : Mean, S.D and t- value							
Emotional Intelligence	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-value	p value	sig
Self Awareness	Male	50	13.90	6.05	6.447	0.000	**
	Female	50	19.82	2.35			
Managing Emotions	Male	50	12.64	5.61	5.779	0.000	**
	Female	50	18.02	3.40			
Motivating Oneself	Male	50	14.10	6.59	3.842	0.000	**
	Female	50	18.22	3.75			
Empathy	Male	50	11.74	5.92	6.633	0.000	**
	Female	50	18.22	3.55			
Emotional Intelligence	Male	50	52.38	21.45	6.529	0.000	**
	Female	50	74.28	10.13			

Note : ** = Significant at 0.01 level

INTERPRETATION

reveals that emotional intelligence between boys and girls had significant at 0.01 level in all sub-components of emotional intelligence like self awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself and empathy. Regarding the understanding level of self awareness, it was concluded that there is significant differences between adolescent boys and girls, because t-value is 6.447,(p=0.01)which is significant on both level. On the basis of Gender, researcher observed that there is significant difference between male and female on the level of understanding emotions because t-value is 6.447,(p=0.01) is significant on both level.

Motivation is the very important part in student life. It is the ladder of success. It is a indicator of emotional intelligence. In the present research when understanding motivation was measured, the result show that female adolescents (F=18.22) had higher level of understanding motivation than female adolescents (M=14.10) (F=18.22). It was also observed that female students were better in understanding motivation (M=14.10) than Male students (M=14.10) (F=18.22).

Managing emotions is the ability to manage and handle relations with others in a better way. On the basis of statistical analysis, founds that F-18.22 which is significant difference in handling relation of adolescents. On the basis of Gender, F value is 3.40 which is significant at both level, Hence it can be concluded that there is a significant difference in handling relation of boys and girls. It was also observed that male students were better in motivating one-self (M=18.22) than female student (F=12.64).

Empathy is a primary factor or backbone of emotional intelligence. According to the study results empathy of adolescents, F value is 3.55 which is significant at 0.00 levels, it means that there is significant of adolescents with respect to empathy. On the basis of mean value, it was concluded that female student (F=18.22) had better empathy than male (M=711.74) students. Regarding Empathy it was assumed that the girls had higher empathy than boys. This hypothesis was accepted because F value is 3.55 which is significant at 0.00 level. In the present research we have observed that the female (F=3.55) had higher empathy than male (M=5.92).

Above all the discussion, it was noticed one thing that adolescents females had higher level of Emotional

intelligence, understanding motivation and Empathy than adolescents males.

Association between the level of Emotional Intelligence with selected Demographic Variables among adolescents

The data presented in above table revealed that there was a statistically significant association between factors of emotional intelligence regarding the effect of demographic variables with age of student (P=0.000), gender of the student (P=0.000), area of residence (P=0.000), medium of instruction of students (P=0.000), group/course of the student (P=0.001), educational status of father (P=0.000), educational status of mother (P=0.000), occupation of head of family (P=0.000), occupation of mother (P=0.004) and residence of student (P=0.002).

There was no statistically significant association between the emotional intelligence vs demographic variables like religion, birth order, type of family and total number of children in the family.

DISCUSSION

This study was under taken to assess level of emotional intelligence among adolescent in selected S.V. Arts college(TTD), Tirupati. The discussion of the present study is based on findings obtained from descriptive and inferential statistical analysis of collected data. It is presented in view of the objective of this study.

OBJECTIVE 1: Assess the level of emotional intelligence among adolescent

The study finding revealed among 100 students 17(17%) had average, 12(12%) had above average, 49(49%) had superior and 22(22%) had excellent level of emotional intelligence.

Consistent with objective 1, the girls showed higher EI than boys in all EI and its four subscales. This finding aligns with previous studies conducted in both adolescents and adults (Cabello et al., 2016a; Dr.Archana and Dr.Anita Swami 2019; Samprity Bhuyan2021; Maniya Anil A. and Chauhan Ajay J.2014). When measuring EI through performance-based ability measures such as the Goleman emotional intelligence test, girls appear to be more emotionally intelligent than boys.

OBJECTIVE 2: To compare the level of emotional intelligence between adolescents boys and girls

Among 100 adolescents comparison of emotional intelligence between boys and girls had more significant at 0.01 level in all sub-components of

emotional intelligence like self awareness, managing emotions, motivating oneself and empathy.

Consistent with objective 2, total EI scores increased with age, and a similar trend was also observed for the using and understanding subscales. However, scores on the perceiving sub scale appeared to decrease with age. To better interpret these findings, it is important to consider the interaction between age and gender (objective 3). Interestingly, the increase in total EI with age was found exclusively among girls, which supports both our objective 3 and finding of the study by (Pooja Veram and Dr.Pubalin Dash 2014, Alberto Megias Robbles et al., 2024, Dr.RabiyaSaboowla et al.,2023) conducted in early adolescence. These results indicate that the development of EI emotional intelligence may follow different trajectories for boys and girls during adolescence. In particular, boys may be at a disadvantage in developing these emotional intelligence and, therefore, may require more support through programs designed to enhance their EI.

CONCLUSION

In this study among 100 adolescent had the level of emotional intelligence 17(17%) were average, 12 (12%) were above average, 49(49%) were superior, 22(22%) were excellent and there is no below average level. The findings of the study revealed that emotional intelligence among adolescent girls were higher than the boys. But the boys were reported to be innovative than the girls. The findings of the study would be helpful in understanding the students and would also be helpful for the teachers, psychologist and counselors to provide proper guidance to the students in various areas and channelized their energy in a proper way for healthy emotional, physical and mental development of the adolescents. Various life skills and personality development programs can be organized in colleges for proper channelization of their energy. There was a statistically significant association between factors of emotional intelligence regarding the effect of demographic variables with age of student ($P=0.000$), gender of the student ($P=0.000$), area of residence ($P=0.000$), medium of instruction of students ($P=0.000$), group/course of the student ($P=0.001$), educational status of father ($P=0.000$), educational status of mother ($P=0.000$), occupation of head of family ($P=0.000$), occupation of mother ($P=0.004$) and residence of student ($P=0.002$). There was no statistically significant association between the emotional intelligence vs

demographic variables like religion, birth order, type of family and total number of children in the family.

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